

Learning to take turns together: The spontaneous emergence of rhythmic coordination

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Abstract

Turn-taking is a feature of many social interactions such as group music-making, where partners must alternate turns with high precision and accuracy. In two studies of musical rhythm coordination, we investigated how joint action partners learn to coordinate the timing of turn-taking. Musically inexperienced individuals learned to tap at the rate of a pacing cue individually or jointly (in turn with a partner), where each tap produced the next tone in a melodic sequence. In Study 1, partners alternated turns every tap, whereas in Study 2 partners alternated turns every two taps. Findings revealed that partners did not achieve the same level of performance accuracy or precision of inter-tap intervals (ITIs) when producing tapping sequences jointly relative to individually, despite showing learning (increased ITI accuracy and precision across the experiment) in both tasks. Strikingly, partners imposed rhythmic patterns onto jointly produced sequences that captured the temporal structure of turns. Together, learning to produce novel temporal sequences in turn with a partner appears to be more challenging than learning to produce the same sequences alone. Critically, partners may impose rhythmic structures onto turn-taking sequences as a strategy for facilitating coordination.

1 Introduction

2 Turn-taking is integral to many social interactions,¹ from conversational speech to group
3 music-making. Turn-taking represents a unique coordination challenge: one partner's
4 actions cannot begin until the other's ends. The ability to seamlessly transition turns is
5 critical for joint actions such as choreographed group dance and music performance, where
6 turns must follow a precise temporal - or rhythmic - structure. Experts in group music and
7 dance can rhythmically alternate turns with seemingly little effort. However, many years of
8 training are often required to achieve this feat. How joint action partners learn to
9 coordinate the timing of turns in rhythmic action sequences like music is not well
10 understood, as most scientific literature on action learning focuses on how individuals
11 learn to perform actions. Several important questions remain to be answered: Do unique
12 learning processes characterize how individuals learn to produce rhythmic action
13 sequences in turn with a partner versus alone? And can turn-taking partners learn to
14 achieve the same levels of temporal accuracy and precision as individuals producing the
15 same rhythmic action sequence? In other words, can turn-taking partners learn to produce
16 actions "as one"?

17 How individuals learn to produce rhythmic action sequences has been widely investigated,
18 and the signatures of learning are well-defined. Individual learning is typically
19 characterized by increases in the temporal accuracy and precision of action sequences
20 relative to a target sequence,²⁻⁵ where accuracy refers to the match between produced and
21 target intervals between successive actions, and precision refers to the consistency of
22 produced intervals. In addition to increases in precision and accuracy, individual learning
23 is also often characterized by changes in error correction patterns over time.⁵ Specifically,
24 temporal errors at early learning stages are often serially dependent - meaning that they
25 are correlated between successive actions - and then at later stages of learning, these serial
26 dependencies are typically reduced.⁵ These three signatures of learning - increased
27 accuracy, precision, and reduced serial dependence of errors - have been observed across a
28 range of repetitive actions, including paced finger-tapping (for a review see Repp & Su,
29 2013)⁶, reaching,⁷ and postural sway⁸; these signatures have also been observed in
30 patterns of spatial error in repetitive spatial tasks such as dart throwing.⁹ Many theories of
31 motor control have emerged to account for these learning signatures and to explain the
32 error correction processes by which individuals optimize performance (for a review see
33 Shadmehr, Smith, & Krakauer (2010) and Latash (2007)).

34 In contrast with individual motor learning, far less is known about the signatures or
35 mechanisms of joint action learning. Only a handful of studies have investigated signatures
36 of joint action learning: these studies reflect a diverse array of tasks (joint spatial
37 coordination,¹⁰⁻¹⁵ music duets,^{16,17} rhythmic finger-tapping with a virtual partner¹⁸),
38 research foci, and learning measures. Moreover, very few of these studies directly compare
39 the signatures of individual and joint action learning for the same action sequence.
40 Knoblich and Jordan (2003) made one of the few direct comparisons between individual
41 and joint action learning in a spatial coordination task. They found that partners'
42 learning rates were slower and accuracy was lower overall relative to individuals

43 performing the same task alone, unless partners received auditory feedback about one
44 another's actions.¹¹ This finding was corroborated by van der Wel et al.,^{13,14} who
45 demonstrated that haptic feedback about a partner's actions leads to the same learning
46 outcomes for joint and individual learning of the same visuo-motor task. Thus, sensory
47 feedback from a partner's actions, which provides information about a partner's action
48 timing, may be an important mechanism for facilitating acquisition of novel joint actions.

49 In rhythmic joint actions such as music and speech conversation, the sensory outcomes of a
50 partners' actions often feature an inherent structure: Musical pitches unfold in an order
51 defined by compositional rules of harmony, and speech prosody and syntax follow specific
52 linguistic patterns. These structures are often highly predictable, which may facilitate
53 temporal coordination above and beyond the mere presence of sensory feedback. For
54 example, the ability to predict the pitch structure of a partner's musical turns may facilitate
55 one's ability to predict when their turns will end and when to begin one's own turns. Lappe
56 et al. (2018) provide some evidence that learning to synchronize one's actions with a
57 metronome is facilitated by the presence of highly predictable sensory feedback.¹⁹
58 However, it is unknown whether joint action learning is optimized when the sensory
59 outcomes of a partners' actions follow a predictable structure, or whether the mere
60 presence of sensory feedback is sufficient for optimal learning.

61 The current study compared how individuals learn novel rhythmic auditory-motor
62 sequences alone versus with a partner. The study focused specifically on how partners
63 learn to take turns in rhythm, due to the high level of temporal coordination required of
64 turn-taking partners and the paucity of literature on how partners learn to take turns.
65 Three main questions were addressed: 1) Do the signatures of individual rhythmic
66 sequence learning (increased temporal precision and accuracy, reduced serial dependency
67 of timing errors) also characterize joint action learning? 2) Can partners achieve the same
68 levels of temporal accuracy and stability as individuals over the same time-course of
69 learning? 3) Does the predictability of sensory information associated with partners'
70 actions facilitate joint action learning?

71 **Methods**

72 **Overview of Studies**

73 The above research questions were addressed in a pseudo-musical sequence learning
74 paradigm for non-experts adapted from previous work:²⁰ Individuals with minimal musical
75 training learned to tap at the rate of an initial metronome pacing cue either alone or in turn
76 with a partner; each successive tap produced the next tone in a pitch sequence that was
77 either predictable (a fixed melody) or random. Participants' main task was therefore to
78 learn to produce inter-tap intervals at the same rate as the metronome cue, and the pitch
79 content served as a potential cue to facilitate coordination.

80 If the signatures of individual learning characterize joint action learning, then turn-taking
81 partners should show increased temporal accuracy and precision, and reduced serial
82 dependency of inter-tap-interval (ITI) errors across learning blocks; moreover, if the

83 partners can learn to “act as one” then these signatures should reach the same levels in
84 joint and individual learning conditions by the end of learning. If the predictability of
85 sensory feedback about a partners’ actions facilitates joint action learning, then partners
86 should show enhanced levels of coordination when learning to produce predictable relative
87 to random pitch sequences. These hypotheses were tested in two joint action learning
88 studies where partners took turns by alternating actions at higher (Study 1) or lower
89 (Study 2) frequencies such that the temporal contingency between actions was either
90 relatively high (Study 1) or low (Study 2).

91 **Study 1**

92 **Participants**

93 48 participants (24 randomly-assigned dyads; 38 female; *M* age = 23.35 years, *SD* = 4.31
94 years) with less than six years of musical training (*M* musical training = .89 years, *SD* = 1.50
95 years, range = 0 - 5 years) were included in the current study sample. Participants were
96 recruited through an online participant database (SONA systems, www.sonasystems.com)
97 and through the local Marton Aron Iskolaszovetkezet Student Organization
98 (<https://www.mads.hu>). All participants in the current sample reported basic English
99 language skills ensuring the ability to understand experiment instructions, right-hand
100 dominance, normal hearing, normal/corrected-normal vision, and no current use or history
101 of psychiatric medication. Participants were screened for training on percussion
102 instruments, which are known to enhance motor and perceptual timing abilities.^{21,22} 4
103 additional dyads completed the study but were excluded from the current sample: 3 of
104 these pairs were excluded due to technical issues during data acquisition; 1 pair was
105 excluded due to a recruitment error. All participants provided informed consent prior to
106 the experiment, and received gift vouchers or money for their participation. The study was
107 approved by the United Ethical Review Committee for Research in Psychology (EPKEB) and
108 was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki (1991).

109 **Stimuli**

110 Two sets of 16-tone isochronous pitch sequences were created for two conditions in the
111 current study: Predictable and Random. Predictable and Random sequences differed in two
112 ways that maximized differences in pitch predictability: First, Predictable sequences were
113 fixed across trials (same sequence on every trial), whereas Random sequences varied
114 across trials (different sequence every trial). Second, Predictable sequences were originally
115 composed to have a predictable harmonic structure, whereas Random sequences were
116 generated by a random algorithm. Methods for generating these sequences are described in
117 turn below. Both sets of sequences used tones drawn exclusively from the key of C-major
118 pentatonic (C4,D4,E4,G4,A4, corresponding to MIDI pitches 60, 62, 64, 67, 69), a 5-tone
119 scale featuring all pitches of the C-major scale except the 4th and 7th scale degrees (F,B),
120 thereby eliminating dissonant intervals. The rationale for use of the C-major pentatonic
121 scale was to ensure that random re-orderings of scale pitches introduced minimal changes
122 in dissonance.

- 123 • **Predictable.** 2 Predictable sequences were composed and counterbalanced across
124 subjects. To generate these sequences, an initial sequence was composed to create an
125 implied harmony that clearly evoked the key of C-major pentatonic, as verified by a
126 trained music theorist: I-vii-I-IV-V-I-V-I- V-I-V-I-ii-I-V-I; pitch sequence = C4, D4, E4,
127 A4, G4, E4, D4, C4, D4, E4, G4, E4, D4, E4, D4, C4). This sequence was then flipped from
128 left to right (retrograde) to create a second sequence. The retrograde and initial
129 sequences were used as the 2 Predictable sequences, and were equivalent with
130 regards to pitch content.
- 131 • **Random.** Random 16-tone pitch sequences were generated in MATLAB using the
132 *randi* function, which generates column vectors of uniformly distributed random
133 integers within a specified range. For each of the 16 sequence positions, *randi*
134 generated 10,000 uniformly distributed random integers between 1 and 5, where
135 integers between 1 and 5 represented the scale degrees of C-major pentatonic. The 16
136 resulting column vectors were horizontally concatenated to produce 10,000 16-
137 integer sequences, where integers at each of the 16 sequence positions were drawn
138 from a uniform random distribution of pitches in the C-major pentatonic scale. The
139 resulting sequences were pruned for sequences containing the same pitch twice in a
140 row and for sequences that did not feature all pitches in the pentatonic scale. This
141 pruning procedure ensured that Predictable and Random pitch sequences featured the
142 same number of unique pitches. 264 sequences remained after pruning. Each Random
143 sequence was subsequently compared (note-by-note) with the two pre-composed
144 Predictable sequences to confirm that the random sequence generation algorithm did
145 not produce any sequences that were by chance identical to the pre-composed
146 sequences.

147 **Hardware and software**

148 Two identical Akai Professional MAX25 keyboards (<https://www.akaipro.com/max25>)
149 were used to record individual and dyadic finger tapping. Musical Instrument Digital
150 Interface (MIDI) information (timing, pitch velocity) was sent from each keyboard over a
151 separate channel; data from the two keyboards were merged via a MIDI merger (MIDI
152 Solutions Inc., Canada), and sent via a MIDI-USB Interface ([https://www.m-
153 audio.com/products/view/uno](https://www.m-audio.com/products/view/uno)) to a Linux computer (Fedora 28, kernel 4.16.3-
154 301.fc28.x86_64) running FTAP MIDI recording software.²³ The version of FTAP used was
155 modified from the 2006 release; this modified version was validated in the first authors'
156 previous work.²⁴ FTAP sent a MIDI message via MIDI-USB to a tone generator (Roland
157 SD50 Mobile Studio Canvas, Roland Corporation, Japan) for every keystroke received,
158 which triggered the tone generator to produce the next pitch in a pre-programmed
159 stimulus sequence. Each pitch was produced using the tone generator's built-in piano
160 timbre (GM2 Instrument Group 001, Piano-1, level = 100). FTAP was also used to generate
161 metronome pacing sequences using the tone generator's built-in woodblock timbre
162 (Rhythm Group 001, Standard-1, level = 100). All piano tones and metronome clicks were
163 programmed in FTAP to have a fixed MIDI velocity (127) and fixed duration. Audio from
164 the tone generator was delivered to participants via headphones (Audio-Technica ATH-
165 M50x Professional Monitor Headphones, Audio-Technica Corporation, United Kingdom) at

166 maximum volume level (volume dial = 10). Each member of a dyad wore separate
167 headphones; headphone pairs were connected to the tone generator phones input jack via
168 a standard headphone splitter.

169 Experimental Design

170 The current study implemented a 2 (Pitch Predictability, between-subject) x 2 (Task,
171 within-subject) x 2 (Learning Block, within-subject) mixed factorial design.

172 • **Pitch Predictability** was manipulated across 2 conditions: *Predictable* and *Random*.
173 Participants in the Predictable condition, heard and produced stimulus pitch
174 sequences that were predictable in two ways: (1) sequences featured a clear pre-
175 defined pentatonic scale structure (see Stimulus section), (2) the same pitch sequence
176 was produced on every trial of the experiment. The two pre-composed Predictable
177 pitch sequences were counterbalanced across participants; partners within a pair
178 received the same pitch sequence.

179 Participants in the Random condition heard and produced pitch sequences that were
180 random in two ways: First, sequences were generated with a random algorithm (see
181 Stimulus section); second, a different random pitch sequence was produced on every
182 trial of the experiment, ensuring that participants could not predict the pitch sequence
183 across trials. Critically, both Predictable and Random conditions were drawn from the
184 pentonic scale and therefore did not differ with regards to frequency of
185 consonant/dissonant intervals.

186 • **Task (2 levels)** was manipulated across 2 conditions: *Individual* and *Joint*. In the
187 Individual condition, participants learned to produce stimulus pitch sequences alone
188 by tapping on a single key on a piano keyboard; every keypress produced audio
189 associated with the next tone in the melody. In the Joint condition, participants
190 learned to produce stimulus pitch sequences with a partner; partners tapped in
191 alternation (first partner 1, then partner 2, then partner 1, etc.; see Figure 1) and each
192 tap produced the next tone in the pitch stimulus sequence. Importantly, auditory
193 outcomes were identical across Individual and Joint conditions, the only difference
194 was whether the pitch sequence was individually or jointly produced.

195 • **Learning Block** featured four levels corresponding to *blocks over which learning was*
196 *expected to occur* (4 total Learning Blocks). Within each Learning Block, participants
197 completed both tasks in a fixed order (counterbalanced across pairs), either Individual
198 followed by Joint or Joint followed by Individual.

Turn-taking patterns in Joint Learning Task

Study 1: **A - B - A - B - A - B - A - B - A - B - A - B - A - B - A - B**

Study 2: **A - A - B - B - A - A - B - B - A - A - B - B - A - A - B - B**

199

200 *Figure 1. Turn-taking patterns in Joint task. Top panel: Turn-taking pattern in the*
201 *Study 1 Joint task, Bottom panel: Turn-taking pattern in the Study 2 Joint task. In*

202 both panels, A (black) denotes tones produced by Partner A and B (gray) denotes
203 tones produced by Partner B. Black dashes indicate inter-tone intervals resolved
204 by Partner A and gray dashes indicate inter-tone intervals resolved by Partner B.
205 In both studies, the partner who started each trial was counterbalanced across
206 Learning Blocks to minimize the emergence of possible leader/follower dynamics.

207 Procedure

208 Participants completed two musical sequence tasks upon arrival at the lab: An Individual
209 task and a Joint task (order counterbalanced). In the Individual task, participants learned to
210 produce pitch sequences alone, and in the Joint task, participants learned to produce pitch
211 sequences with a partner (see above). These tasks were interleaved across 4 Learning
212 Blocks. For both tasks the procedure was the same within each block, featuring a Listen
213 phase, a Practice phase, and a Test phase:

- 214 • **Listen Phase (<=2 trials).** In the Listen phase of each task, participants heard a MIDI
215 recording of either the same melody that they would subsequently produce
216 (Predictable), or a pitch sequence that was generated using the same algorithm
217 (Random). Pitch sequences were presented at a rate of 120 BPM (500 millisecond
218 inter-onset interval), corresponding to the center of the range in which music is
219 typically produced.²⁵

220 The experimenter instructed participants as follows (curly brackets enclose distinct
221 instructions for Individual/Joint tasks, square brackets enclose distinct instructions
222 for the Predictable/Random tasks):

223 *"We will let you listen to [the melody that you will produce (Predictable) / a sample
224 melody (Random)]. [The sample melody is in the same style and will sound like the
225 melodies that you will produce (Random only)]. Please listen carefully, and use this as an
226 opportunity to get an idea of how you should aim to sound when you {produce the
227 melody yourself (Individual) / when you produce the melody together (Joint)}.*

228 Participants were allowed to hear up to two trials of the pitch sequence (1 trial = 1
229 sequence iteration). The goal of this Listen phase was to expose participants to an
230 "ideal" performance of the pitch sequence with regards to timing and fluency.

- 231 • **Practice Phase (2 trials).** After the Listen phase, participants completed the Practice
232 phase in which they practiced producing the same stimulus sequence they heard
233 during Listen. Participants either produced the melody alone (Individual) or with a
234 partner (Joint), depending on the task.

235 Participants in the Individual Task were instructed as follows:

236 *"Now you have the chance to produce this sample melody... you will produce this melody
237 by tapping on the piano key; every time you tap you will hear the next tone in the melody.
238 Your goal will be to produce the melody so that it sounds like what you heard during
239 Listening. The tempo at which you should produce the melody will be indicated by a
240 metronome cue at the beginning of each trial."*

241 Participants in the Joint Task were instructed as follows:

242 *“Now you have the chance to produce this sample melody together...On each trial,*
243 *Partner A will produce the first melody tone by tapping on their designated key, then*
244 *Partner B will tap the next melody tone by pressing on their designated key, then Partner*
245 *A will produce the third melody tone by tapping on their key, and so forth.”*

246 *“Your goal will be to co-produce the melody so that what you co-produce sounds like*
247 *what you heard during listening. The tempo at which you should take turns producing*
248 *melody tones will be indicated by a metronome cue at the beginning of each trial.”*

249 On each practice trial, participants heard 8 metronome clicks at a rate of 120 BPM
250 (500 millisecond inter-onset interval, IOI), and were instructed to start tapping when
251 the metronome stopped and to continue tapping until they heard no more sound. The
252 sound on each trial cut out after participants produced 16 taps (see above).

253 Participants were allowed up to two practice trials (1 trial = 1 iteration of the stimulus
254 sequence); in the Joint task, practice trials were only counted if they reflected the
255 correct (instructed) turn-taking pattern, and the experimenter gave feedback on
256 accuracy after each trial.

257 • **Test Phase (9 test trials).** After the Practice phase, participants completed the Test
258 phase. In this Test phase, participants produced either the same stimulus melody as
259 during Practice (Predictable), or produced a melody generated using the same
260 algorithm (Random). Instructions were identical to the Practice phase, except that
261 participants in the Random condition were told that their taps would generate a
262 different pitch sequence on each trial. Participants completed a total of 9 test trials; in
263 the Joint task, only “correct” trials were counted towards this total, and participants
264 had to continue the task until they produced 9 correct trials. The experimenter
265 pointed out errors in turn-taking accuracy and did not comment on trials where the
266 turn-taking was correct.

267 **Study 2**

268 Turn-taking structure may influence how partners learn to coordinate joint actions. For
269 example, partners may correct interval timing in a turn-taking sequence differently
270 depending on whether the interval was jointly produced (occurred at a turn-transition) or
271 individually produced (occurred within a turn). Study 1 could not test this possibility
272 because all intervals were jointly produced. Study 2 replicated Study 1 but with a different
273 turn-taking structure: Partners produce pitch sequences at a cued rate by alternating every
274 two taps instead of every tap. Therefore, each Joint action sequence featured intervals that
275 were both individually produced (occurred within a turn) or jointly produced (occurred
276 between turns). Additionally, Study 2 used exclusively Random pitch sequences (same as
277 Random Pitch condition from Study 1), as Study 1 did not yield an effect of Pitch
278 Predictability (see Results).

279 **Participants**

280 24 participants (12 randomly-assigned dyads; 15 female; M age = 23.88 years, SD = 3.35
281 years; 23 right-handed, 1 ambidextrous) with less than six years of musical training (M
282 musical training = 1.21 years, SD = 1.75 years, range = 0 - 5 years) were included in Study 2.
283 The number of participants was determined based on the number of participants in each
284 experimental group in Study 1. Participants were recruited through an online participant
285 database (SONA systems, www.sonasystems.com) and through the local Marton Aron
286 Iskolaszovetkezet Student Organization (<https://www.mads.hu>). All participants in Study 2
287 were recruited using the same criteria as Study 1. One additional pair was recruited but
288 excluded from the study due to a technical issue during recording. All participants provided
289 informed consent prior to the experiment, and received gift vouchers or money for their
290 participation. The study was approved by the United Ethical Review Committee for
291 Research in Psychology (EPKEB) and was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of
292 Helsinki (1991).

293 **Stimuli**

294 Study 2 stimuli comprised the same pitch sequences as the Random condition in Study 1
295 (see above).

296 **Design and Procedure**

297 Study 2 followed an identical Design and Procedure to Study 1, except that only Random
298 pitch sequences were used (i.e., factors were Task x Learning Block, no Pitch Predictability
299 factor), and partners observed a different turn-taking sequence during the Joint task (see
300 Figure 1). Specifically, partners in Study 2 alternated producing every two tones, such that
301 the turn-taking sequence for the 16-tone was: A - A - B - B - A - A - B - B - A - A - B - B -
302 A - A - B - B, where A = tone produced by partner A and B = tone produced by partner B.
303 The partner who started each Joint learning trial was counterbalanced across learning
304 Blocks. The rationale behind this change in turn-taking pattern was to determine whether
305 the temporal patterning observed in Study 1 extends to different forms of turn-taking.

306 **Data processing and analysis**

307 Data associated with Studies 1 and 2 were pre-processed and analyzed using
308 corresponding procedures.

309 MIDI keystroke data were pre-processed in MATLAB R2017a using custom scripts, and all
310 statistical tests were performed in RStudio v1.2.1335 running R v3.6.0. Specifically, all data
311 were submitted to ANOVAs implemented using the *R aov_ez* function in the *afex* package
312 v.23-0, which uses Type-III Sum-of-Squares, and applies Greenhouse-Geiser correction for
313 violations of sphericity for within-subject factors. Follow-up comparisons were
314 implemented using the *emmeans* package v.1.3.5, which by default uses effects coding
315 (contr.sum) with *afex* objects. The *emmeans* model was changed from the default univariate
316 model to a multivariate model (*afex_options(emmeans_model = "multivariate")*), which
317 provides better correction for violations of sphericity (<https://cran.r->

318 project.org/web/packages/afex/afex.pdf). Plots were created using *afex_plots()* in the *afex*
319 package and custom *R* code.

320 Pre-processing

- 321 • **Onset extraction and ITI calculation.** Tap onsets were extracted from MIDI files
322 (timestamps, pitch, velocity) and inter-tap intervals (ITIs) between successive taps
323 were computed for each Test trial.
- 324 • **Trial exclusion.** Test trials in the Joint Learning condition were flagged for exclusion
325 during online data acquisition if partners did not observe the correct turn-taking
326 structure for the respective study. Trials were reassessed offline for turn-taking
327 accuracy, and all trials flagged as inaccurate were subsequently excluded from
328 analyses. Rare trials in which technical error occurred during data acquisition were
329 flagged online by the experimenter, and were also excluded from offline analyses.
- 330 • **ITI outlier exclusion.** Rare ITI outliers were identified and excluded from all analyses,
331 excepting lag auto-correlations and analyses based on IOI contrasts, both of which
332 require continuous time-series, and are susceptible to biases introduced by outlier
333 replacement. ITI outliers were defined within-subject for the Individual task, and
334 within-pair for the Joint task. ITIs for each subject/pair were aggregated across all
335 Learning Blocks to form a single task-specific distribution, and outliers in each
336 distribution were identified as values exceeding 3 scaled median absolute deviations
337 from the median of a distribution (using *isoutlier.m* in MATLAB).²⁶ This method is less
338 susceptible than traditional- mean-based methods to false negatives in outlier
339 detection.²⁷ Excluded ITIs were replaced with *NaNs* and (*nanmean.m* in MATLAB was
340 subsequently used for all averaging).

341 Calculation and analysis of dependent measures

342 Three primary dependent measures were computed from ITI data: accuracy, precision, and
343 lag autocorrelations. ITI accuracy and precision provide insight into participants' overall
344 ability to maintain the cued rate of ITI production, whereas lag autocorrelations capture
345 finer-grained temporal patterns, such as serial dependence and rhythmicity between ITIs.
346 Described below is the specific rationale for each dependent measure, as well as the
347 method for calculation and analysis.

348 ITI accuracy

- 349 • **Rationale.** ITI accuracy captures how well participants were able to maintain the cued
350 target ITI (500 ms). Accuracy was measured as percent deviation from the target ITI. If
351 participants exhibit learning, then accuracy should increase across Learning Blocks
352 (reflected as decreased percent deviation from the target ITI) in both Individual and
353 Joint Learning. Moreover, equivalent levels of accuracy should be observed between
354 Individual and Joint tasks by the final experiment block, if partners learn to “perform
355 as one”.
- 356 • **Calculation.** To compute ITI accuracy, ITIs on each trial were expressed as absolute
357 percent deviation from the target ITI of 500 ms i.e. $(\text{abs}(500 - \text{ITI}) / 500) * 100$.

358 Absolute percent deviation values were averaged across ITIs within each trial, and
359 then across trials for each participant within each Learning Block/Task.

360 • **Analysis.** Mean accuracy values for Study 1 were subsequently submitted to a 2 x 4 x 2
361 mixed ANOVA with within-subject factors of Task (Individual/Joint) and Learning
362 Block (1-4), and the between-subjects factor of Pitch Predictability
363 (Predictable/Random). Pair was the grouping (ID) variable. Mean accuracy values for
364 Study 2 were submitted to a 4 x 2 repeated-measures ANOVA with factors of Task
365 (Individual/Joint) and Learning Block (1-4), also with Pair as the ID variable.

366 ITI precision

367 • **Rationale.** ITI precision captures the extent to which participants produced stable
368 temporal intervals. ITI precision was assessed using the Coefficient of ITI Variation
369 ($CV(ITI)$, see calculation below), which measures ITI variability as a proportion of ITI
370 duration, therefore controlling for the relationship between speed and variability. ITI
371 precision should increase across Learning blocks (reflected as decreased Coefficient of
372 Variation) in both Individual and Joint tasks if participants exhibit learning. Moreover,
373 equivalent levels of $CV(ITI)$ should be observed between Individual and Joint tasks by
374 the final experiment block, if partners learn to “perform as one”.

375 • **Calculation.** $CV(ITI)$ was computed on each trial as $SD(ITI_{trial}) / Mean(ITI_{trial})$, and
376 then averaged across trials for each subject within task and Block.

377 • **Analysis.** Mean $CV(ITI)$ values for Study 1 were subsequently submitted to a 2 x 4 x 2
378 mixed ANOVA with the between-subjects factor of Pitch Predictability
379 (Predictable/Random), and the within-subject factors of Task (Individual/Joint) and
380 Learning Block (1-4). Pair was the ID variable. Mean $CV(ITI)$ values for Study 2 were
381 submitted to a 4 x 2 repeated-measures ANOVA with factors of Task (Individual/Joint)
382 and Learning Block (1-4), with Pair as the ID variable.

383 Lag autocorrelations

384 • **Rationale.** Non-experts in motor behaviours such as dance and music performance
385 often display greater rigidity of domain-specific movements than experts.^{8,20,28} Rigidity
386 is often characterized by rhythmical patterning of temporal intervals between
387 successive movements.⁵ Specifically, previous work on finger-tapping indicates that
388 rhythmicity is characterized by regular durational alternation between successive ITIs,
389 such that participants alternately shorten and lengthen successive ITIs, resulting in a
390 *long-short-long-short* or *short-long-short-long* pattern.⁵
391 If participants in the current study exhibit learning, then it would be expected that ITI
392 rhythmicity should decrease over the course across Learning Blocks. Moreover,
393 similar levels of rhythmicity should be observed between Individual and Joint tasks by
394 the final experiment block if partners learn to “perform as one”. Finally, rhythmicity
395 may arise as a function of turn-taking structure.

396 To capture temporal patterns arising from the distinct turn-taking structures in
397 Studies 1 and 2, lag autocorrelations were computed at lags 1, 2, and 4. Lag 1 captures
398 patterns between serial ITIs (similar to ITI contrasts), whereas lags 2 and 4 capture

399 patterns spanning intervals of 2 and 4 ITIs, which respectively correspond to the turn-
400 taking rate (lag 2) and turn cycle duration (lag 4; time to complete a full turn cycle
401 where each partner completes their turn once) in Study 2. Therefore, autocorrelations
402 at lags 2 and 4 should differ between studies if turn-taking structure gives rise to
403 distinct temporal patterns. Autocorrelations at lag 1 should simply confirm patterns
404 revealed by ITI contrasts. Lag autocorrelation magnitude would be expected to
405 decrease over the course of experiment blocks if learning is reflected in decreased
406 long-range temporal patterns. Moreover, lag autocorrelations should not differ
407 between Individual and Joint tasks by the final Learning Block if partners learn to
408 “perform as one”.

409 • **Calculation.** To compute lag autocorrelations, linear trends in ITI series were first
410 removed from each trial prior (MATLAB function *detrend.m*), as linear drift can bias
411 autocorrelation outcomes. Detrended ITI series were assessed for autocorrelations
412 (MATLAB function *autocorr.m* in the Econometrics Toolbox), and the resulting
413 autocorrelations were subsequently averaged across trials at lags 1, 2, and 4 for each
414 subject within task and Block. Outlier ITIs were retained in autocorrelation analyses to
415 avoid breaking serial dependencies between successive ITIs, which are critical to the
416 lag structure.

417 • **Analysis.** *Within-study comparisons.* Lag autocorrelations for Study 1 were
418 subsequently submitted to a 2 x 2 x 4 x 3 mixed ANOVA, with between-subjects factor
419 of Pitch Predictability (Predictable/Random), and within-subjects factors of Task
420 (Individual/Joint), Learning Block (1-4), and Lag (1/2/4). Lag autocorrelations for
421 Study 2 were submitted to a 2 x 4 x 3 repeated-measures ANOVA, with factors of Task
422 (Individual/Joint), Learning Block (1-4), and Lag (1,2,4). Pair was defined as the ID
423 variable for both ANOVAs.

424 *Between-study comparisons.* Lag correlations were also directly compared across
425 studies. Trial-mean lag correlations from Studies 1 and 2 were submitted to a 2 x 2 x 4
426 x 3 mixed ANOVA, with between-subjects factor of Study (1/2), and within-subject
427 factors of Task (Individual/Joint), Learning Block (1-4), and Lag (1/2/4). Pair was ID
428 variable. Only Study 1 participants who completed the Random Pitch condition were
429 included in this ANOVA so as to ensure equal samples across studies (N=12 pairs per
430 study), and identical task features excepting turn-taking structure.

431 Results

432 Learning effects revealed by ITI accuracy and precision across studies

433 ITI accuracy

434 Study 1

435 Figure 2a shows changes in ITI accuracy across Learning Blocks for each task in Study 1.
436 The 2 x 4 x 2 ANOVA on ITI accuracy revealed significant main effects of Learning Block,
437 $F(1,7782, 39.1195) = 9.0615, p = 0.0009, ges = 0.0468$, Task, $F(1, 22) = 90.6916, p = 0.0000$,

438 $g_{es} = 0.4307$, and a significant Task x Learning Block interaction, $2.2793, 50.1436) =$
 439 $4.2849, p = 0.0154, g_{es} = 0.0159$. No other effects or interactions were significant (all p 's >
 440 $.1$).

441
 442 *Figure 2. ITI Precision & Accuracy.* Top row: Mean ITI accuracy (percent deviation
 443 from metronome-cued ITI) across Learning Blocks for Studies 1 (Panel A) and 2

444 (Panel B). Bottom row: Mean ITI precision (Coefficient of Variation, $CV(ITI)$)
445 across Learning Blocks for Studies 1 (Panel C) and 2 (Panel D). In all panels,
446 Individual and Joint tasks are displayed in dark and light blue respectively, and
447 error bars reflect within-subject 95% Confidence Intervals (CIs).

448 Follow-up linear contrast analyses revealed significant linear effects of Block on ITI
449 accuracy in both the Individual Task, $t(22) = -2.4390, p = 0.0233$, and the Joint Task, $t(22) =$
450 $-3.6430, p = .0014$. Negative contrast estimates were observed in both Tasks (Individual: -
451 3.8520 ; Joint: -12.5927), indicating improved ITI accuracy across Learning Blocks (reduced
452 percent deviation from the target ITI). A linear interaction contrast (contrast of contrasts)
453 revealed a stronger linear effect in the Joint than the Individual task, $t(22) = 2.7859, p =$
454 0.0108 , indicating more improvement across blocks in Joint relative to Individual Learning.
455 However, partners in the Joint task did not reach Individual accuracy levels: Pairwise
456 comparisons (Tukey-corrected) indicated that accuracy was significantly lower for the
457 Joint relative to the Individual task across all Learning Blocks (all p 's $< .001$).

458 **Study 2**

459 Figure 2b shows changes in ITI accuracy across Learning Blocks for each task in Study 2.
460 The 4×2 repeated-measures ANOVA on ITI accuracy revealed significant main effects of
461 Learning Block, $F(1.7314, 19.0459) = 10.5204, p = 0.0012, ges = 0.1068$, and Task, $F(1, 11)$
462 $= 19.2066, p = 0.0011, ges = 0.1627$. No other effects or interactions were significant (all p 's
463 $> .1$).

464 Follow-up linear contrast analyses revealed a significant linear effect of Block on ITI
465 accuracy in the Joint task, $t(11) = -3.4566, p = .0054$, and a marginal linear effect in the
466 Individual task, $t(11) = -1.9041, p = 0.0834$. Negative contrast estimates were observed in
467 both Tasks (Individual: -8.3332 ; Joint: -16.9328), indicating improvement in accuracy
468 across Learning Blocks in both Individual and Joint Learning. No linear interaction contrast
469 was computed because, unlike Study 1, the ANOVA on ITI accuracy did not yield a
470 significant interaction between task and Learning Block. However, partners in the Joint
471 task did not reach Individual accuracy levels: Pairwise comparisons indicated that accuracy
472 was significantly lower for the Joint relative to the Individual task across all Learning
473 Blocks (all p 's $< .05$), except for Block 4, where there was a marginal overlap in Individual
474 and Joint accuracy ($p = .0747$).

475 **ITI Precision**

476 **Study 1**

477 Figure 2c shows changes in ITI precision across Learning Blocks for each task in Study 1.
478 The $2 \times 4 \times 2$ ANOVA on ITI precision also revealed significant main effects of Learning
479 Block, $F(2.4035, 52.8760) = 14.9768, p = 0.0000, ges = 0.0609$, Task, $F(1, 22) = 102.3690, p$
480 $= 0.0000, ges = 0.6163$, and a significant Task \times Learning Block interaction, $2.5849,$
481 $56.8689) = 10.0374, p = 0.0000, ges = 0.0347$. No other effects or interactions were
482 significant (all p 's $> .1$).

483 Follow-up linear contrast analyses again revealed significant linear effects of Block on ITI
484 precision in both the Individual task, $t(22) = -4.1073, p = 0.0005$, and the Joint task, $t(22) =$
485 $-5.1224, p < 0.0001$. Both Tasks showed negative contrast estimates (Individual: -0.0162 ;
486 Joint: -0.1072), reflecting decreased variability and improved ITI precision across Learning
487 Blocks. An interaction contrast revealed a stronger linear effect in the Joint than the
488 Individual task, $t(22) = 4.5422, p = 0.0002$. However, partners in the Joint task did not
489 reach Individual precision levels: Pairwise comparisons indicated that precision was
490 significantly lower for the Joint relative to the Individual task across all Learning Blocks (all
491 p 's $< .001$).

492 **Study 2**

493 Figure 2d shows changes in ITI precision across Learning Blocks for each Task in Study 2.
494 The 4 x 2 ANOVA on ITI precision also revealed significant main effects of Learning Block,
495 $F(1.3024, 14.3259) = 12.5350, p = 0.0019, ges = 0.0856$, Task, $F(1, 11) = 25.4283, p =$
496 $0.0004, ges = 0.3124$, and a significant Task x Learning Block interaction, $F(2.0152,$
497 $22.1668) = 5.6276, p = 0.0104, ges = 0.0347$.

498 Follow-up linear contrast analyses revealed significant linear effects of Block on ITI
499 precision in Joint, $t(11) = -3.8778, p = 0.0026$, but not Individual Learning ($p = .1139$). Joint
500 Learning showed negative contrast estimates, -0.1452 (reflecting decrease in percent
501 deviation from the target ITI), indicating improved ITI accuracy across Learning Blocks. An
502 interaction contrast confirmed a stronger linear effect in the Joint than the Individual task,
503 $t(11) = 2.6729, p = 0.0217$. However, partners in the Joint task did not reach Individual
504 precision levels: Pairwise comparisons indicated that precision was significantly lower for
505 the Joint relative to the Individual task across all Learning Blocks (all p 's $< .01$).

506 **Distinct rhythms of joint action across studies revealed by lag autocorrelations**

507 **Study 1**

508 Figure 2a displays mean ITI autocorrelations for Study 1. The 2 x 2 x 4 x 3 ANOVA on
509 autocorrelations at lags 1, 2, and 4 revealed significant main effects of Task, $F(1, 22) =$
510 $71.9135, p = 0.0000, ges = 0.1600$, Lag, $F(1.8301, 40.2630) = 122.4648, p < 0.0001, ges =$
511 0.6358 , and a significant Task x Lag interaction, $F(1.6840, 37.0476) = 33.5599, p = 0.0000, ges$
512 $= 0.2036$. A marginal main effect of Learning Block was also observed, $F(56.9056) = 2.9310, p$
513 $= 0.0484, ges = 0.0048$. No other effects or interactions were significant (all p 's $> .1$).

514

515 *Figure 2. Autocorrelations at lags related to turn-taking.* Boxplots displaying mean
 516 autocorrelations at lags 1, 2, and 4 for Study 1 (Panel A) and Study 2 (Panel B) for
 517 Individual (dark blue) and Joint (light blue) tasks. Boxplots display the median of
 518 each distribution (horizontal lines), where and lower and upper hinges reflect
 519 25% and 75% around the median, and upper and lower whiskers reflect +/- 1.5 x
 520 the Inter-Quartile Interval for the distribution (default statistical settings in
 521 *geom_boxplot()* in the *ggplot2* R package, as called from *afex_plot*).

522 Significant main effects and interactions were followed up by pairwise comparisons using
 523 the *contrast()* call in the *emmeans* package (method="pairwise"), with Tukey-correction
 524 applied in the case of multiple comparisons. Follow-up comparisons for the main effect of
 525 Task revealed more negative mean lag autocorrelations for Joint ($M = -0.1876$, $SE = 0.0096$)
 526 relative to Individual ($M = -0.1090$, $SE = 0.0034$) Learning ($t(22) = -8.4802$, $p < 0.0001$).
 527 Follow-up comparisons for the main effect of Lag revealed significantly more negative
 528 mean lag autocorrelations for Lag 1 ($M = -0.3163$, $SE = 0.0143$) relative to Lag 2 ($M = -$
 529 0.0692 , $SE = 0.0122$), $t(22) = -12.0117$, $p < 0.0001$, and relative to Lag 4 ($M = -0.0594$, $SE =$
 530 0.0093), $t(22) = -13.3578$, $p < 0.0001$. No differences were observed between Lags 2 and 4
 531 ($p > .1$). Critically, follow-up comparisons for the two-way interaction between Task x Lag
 532 revealed that the difference between Individual and Joint tasks was driven by significantly
 533 greater magnitude of negative autocorrelations at Lag 1 for the Joint task ($M = -0.4198$, $SE =$
 534 0.0225) relative to the Individual task ($M = -0.2128$, $SE = 0.0124$), $t(22) = -9.1798$, $p <$
 535 0.0001 . In contrast, autocorrelations at lags 2 and 4 did not differ between Individual and
 536 Joint tasks.

537 Study 2

538 Figure 2b displays mean ITI autocorrelations for Study 2. The 2 x 4 x 3 ANOVA on
539 autocorrelations at lags 1, 2, and 4 revealed significant main effects of task, $F(1, 11) =$
540 $26.0066, p = 0.0003, ges = 0.0625$, Lag, $F(1.4069, 15.4754) = 49.0705, p < 0.0001, ges =$
541 0.5718 , and a significant task x Lag interaction, $F(1.6348, 2.8634, 17.9824) = 16.6268, p =$
542 $0.0002, ges = 0.3113$. A marginal interaction between Learning Block and Lag was also
543 observed, $F(1.6348, 17.9824) = 16.6268, p = 0.0002, ges = 0.3113$. No other effects or
544 interactions were significant (all p 's $> .1$).

545 Significant main effects and interactions were followed up by pairwise comparisons using
546 the *contrast()* call in the *emmeans* package (method="pairwise"), with Tukey-correction
547 applied in the case of multiple comparisons. Follow-up comparisons for the main effect of
548 Task revealed more positive mean lag autocorrelations for Joint ($M = -0.0407, SE = 0.0157$)
549 relative to Individual ($M = -0.1091, SE = 0.0052$ Learning, $t(11) = 5.0997, p = 0.0003$.
550 Follow-up comparisons for the main effect of Lag revealed marginally more negative mean
551 lag autocorrelations for Lag 1 ($M = -0.2373, SE = 0.0198$) relative to Lag 2 ($M = -0.1175, SE$
552 $= 0.0305, t(11) = -2.4717, p = 0.0736$, and significantly more negative Lag 1
553 autocorrelations relative to Lag 4 ($M = 0.1302, SE = 0.0197$), $t(11) = -11.0619, p < 0.0001$.
554 No differences were observed between Lags 2 and 4 ($p > .1$). Critically, follow-up
555 comparisons for the two-way interaction between task x Lag revealed that the difference
556 between Individual and Joint Learning was driven by significantly more positive
557 autocorrelations at Lag 4 for Joint ($M = 0.2900, SE = 0.0386$) relative to Individual Learning
558 ($M = -0.0295, SE = 0.0103$), $t(11.0000) = 7.8939, p < 0.0001$. Autocorrelations at lags 1 and 2
559 were both negative (Lag 2 $M = -0.1547, SE = 0.0550$), and did not differ between Individual
560 and Joint Learning.

561 **Cross-study comparison of temporal patterns arising from turn-taking structure**

562 Autocorrelations at lags 1, 2, and 4 were compared across studies (Random Pitch pairs
563 only) to quantify the extent to which distinct temporal patterns arise from turn-taking
564 structure. Autocorrelations at lag1 reflect the turn-taking structure of Study 1, whereas lags
565 at 2 and 4 reflect the turn-taking structure of Study 2 (where lag2 reflects the inter-turn
566 interval, and lag4 reflects a full turn cycle, i.e. the intervals across which both partners
567 complete their turn). The 2 x 2 x 4 x 3 ANOVA on autocorrelations at lags 1, 2, and 4
568 revealed significant main effects of Study, $F(1, 22) = 29.0498, p < 0.0001, ges = 0.0756$, and
569 Lag, $F(1.5572, 34.2588) < 0.0001, ges = 0.5659$, suggesting study-specific rhythmic patterns
570 in ITI structure. Significant interactions were also observed between Study x Task,
571 $F(1.0000, 22.0000) = 54.4636, p = 0.0000, ges = 0.0921$, Study x Lag, $F(1.5572, 34.2588) =$
572 $13.0538, p = 0.0002, ges = 0.1452$, Task x Lag, $F(1.6905, 37.1910) = 23.8794, p = 0.0000, ges$
573 $= 0.2240$, and Study x Task x Lag, $F(1.6905, 37.1910) = 10.7532, p = 0.0004, ges = 0.1150$.
574 Together, these significant interactions indicate that the rhythmic structure of ITI
575 sequences captured by lags-1, 2, and 4 differ across Studies and Tasks. Marginal
576 interactions were observed between Task x Learning Block, $F(2.5468, 56.0287) = 2.6756, p$
577 $= 0.0647, ges = 0.0030$, and between Learning Block and Lag, $F(2.5468, 87.0812) = 2.2312,$
578 $p = 0.0728, ges = 0.0116$, but these were not followed up because they were only marginally
579 significant, and because visual inspection of the interaction means did not reflect Learning.
580 No other effects or interactions were significant (all p 's $> .1$).

581 To assess how the rhythmic structure of ITIs differed across studies and tasks, the
582 significant three-way interaction between Study x Lag x Task was followed up by Tukey-
583 adjusted pairwise comparisons between estimated marginal means using the *contrast()* call
584 in the *emmeans* package (method="pairwise"). These comparisons revealed that Lag 1
585 autocorrelations were significantly more negative in Study 1 ($M = -0.4360$, $SE = 0.0343$)
586 relative to Study 2 ($M = -0.2573$, $SE = 0.0343$) for Joint Learning only, $t(22) = -3.6868$, $p =$
587 0.0013 . Additionally, Lag 4 autocorrelations were significantly more positive in Study 2 (M
588 $= -0.0295$, $SE = 0.0090$) relative to Study 1 ($M = -0.0440$, $SE = 0.0090$) for Joint Learning
589 only, $t(22) = -7.3140$, $p < 0.0001$. No other pairwise comparisons between marginal means
590 for levels of Study x Lag x Task were significant (all p 's $> .1$).

591 The study-specific rhythmic patterns in the Joint task captured by lag autocorrelations can
592 be clearly visualized using ITI contrasts, which code for directional change between
593 successive ITIs. Figure 3 shows mean ITI contrasts across Studies and Tasks. Details on ITI
594 contrast calculation are reported in the Supplementary Material.

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Figure 3. Illustration of study-specific rhythmic patterns. ITI contrast plots display patterns of durational change between successive ITIs, and clearly capture rhythmic patterns and changes in rhythmicity across ITIs in a sequence. The current figure displays mean ITI contrasts computed for Study 1 (Panel A) and Study 2 (Panel C) for Individual and Joint tasks, shown against an exemplar

601 contrast pattern (black dotted line) representing perfect rhythmicity (negative
602 lag1 autocorrelation of 1.0). The mean geometric distance (Manhattan distance)
603 to the exemplar at each ITI sequence position is also shown here for Study 1
604 (Panel B) and Study anel C) to illustrate average changes in ITI rhythmicity over
605 the course of a trial. Mean contrast values of .5 reflect no durational change
606 between successive ITIs, mean contrast values above .5 reflect the same direction
607 of durational change as the first pair of ITIs in the sequence, and values below .5
608 reflect the opposite direction of durational change as the first pair of ITIs. The
609 figure clearly displays the enhanced rhythmicity of Joint relative to Individual ITI
610 sequences in both studies, and that these rhythmicities depend upon turn-taking
611 structure. Moreover, rhythmic patterns in Study 1 appear to change over time,
612 indicating within-trial learning. It should be noted that only ITI contrasts 2-14 are
613 shown in each plot because the first ITI contrast on each trial was by default
614 assigned a value of 1. Details of the methods for computing ITI contrasts are
615 provided in the Supplementary Material.

616 Discussion

617 The current study investigated how individuals learn to produce novel temporal sequences
618 alone versus with a partner. A pseudo-musical sequence production task was used that
619 allowed non-musicians to produce musical sequences without learning how to play an
620 instrument. In this task, participants tapped a single key on a piano keyboard at a cued rate,
621 and each subsequent tap produced the next tone in a melody. Participants completed this
622 task alone (Individual) and in turn with a partner (Joint), with the goal of producing stable
623 temporal intervals at the cued rate. The joint turn-taking structure was manipulated across
624 two studies such that turn-taking frequency was either high (Study 1, A-B-A-B turn-taking
625 pattern) or low (Study 2, A-A-B-B pattern). In Study 1, the predictability of pitch sequences
626 was also manipulated, such that pitch sequences were either predictable or random. Three
627 main questions were addressed across studies: 1) Do the signatures of individual temporal
628 sequence learning (increased temporal precision and accuracy, reduced serial dependency
629 of timing errors) also characterize joint action learning? 2) Can partners achieve the same
630 levels of temporal accuracy and stability as individuals over the same time-course of
631 learning? 3) Does the predictability of sensory information associated with partners'
632 actions facilitate joint action learning? Findings are discussed below with regards to each of
633 these questions.

634 Turn-taking partners do not learn to perform “as one”

635 Participants displayed two classic signatures of learning in both studies and in both
636 Individual and Joint tasks, namely improved temporal accuracy and precision with training.
637 Improvements in accuracy were reflected by the linear reduction in percent deviation of
638 observed inter-tap intervals (ITIs) from the cued interval (500 ms) across Learning Blocks.
639 Improvements in temporal precision were reflected by the linear reduction in coefficient of
640 ITI variation ($CV(ITI)$) - a measure of ITI variability that expresses variability as a
641 proportion of duration - across Learning blocks.

642 Learning trajectories for both accuracy and precision were steeper for the Joint relative to
643 the Individual task (indicated by contrasts of linear contrasts), giving rise to interaction
644 effects between Block and Task (for precision in both studies, and for accuracy in Study 1).
645 These differences in learning trajectories between tasks likely arise from the fact that
646 accuracy and precision were closer to ceiling in the first Learning Block in the individual
647 relative to the Joint task. Despite these improvements with training, partners in the Joint
648 task were unable to achieve Individual levels of temporal precision and accuracy.
649 Specifically, accuracy and precision were reduced across all Learning Blocks in the Joint
650 relative to the Individual task, though in Study 1 Joint accuracy marginally approached
651 Individual levels by the final block.

652 Taken together, learning to co-produce temporal intervals in turn with a partner - at high
653 and low turn-taking frequencies - appears to be more challenging than producing intervals
654 alone. Partners are worse than individuals at matching the tempo of a cued target interval
655 and are less able to produce stable temporal intervals despite equal training, though they
656 do show improvements over time. Reduced temporal precision and accuracy for co-
657 produced relative to individually produced intervals may arise from differences in
658 partners' temporal error correction processes, as temporal error correction is known to
659 vary widely between individuals.²⁹ Another possibility is that underlying oscillatory
660 processes related to partners' timekeeping - such as differences in partners' natural
661 frequencies of tapping - moderate the accuracy and stability with which partners co-
662 produce temporal intervals. Future work should investigate these possible underlying
663 mechanisms.

664 **Turn-taking structure is reflected in rhythmic patterns that emerge during joint** 665 **learning**

666 Lag autocorrelation findings from the current study reveal that joint action partners
667 produce rhythmic patterns of error typically associated with novice motor behaviours. In
668 Study 1, partners displayed an alternating long-short (or short-long) pattern of ITIs,
669 captured by a negative lag1 autocorrelation and illustrated by ITI contrasts plots. This
670 pattern was largely attenuated for individually produced sequences, and visualizations of
671 ITI contrasts indicate that the pattern diminished across ITIs within trials, suggesting that
672 within-trial learning took place. In Study 2, partners also displayed rhythmic patterns of
673 ITIs at the study-specific turn-cycle interval - namely at a lag of 4 ITIs. This pattern was not
674 present for individually produced sequences and is also clearly illustrated by ITI contrast
675 plots.

676 Direct statistical comparisons of lag autocorrelations between studies confirmed that
677 rhythmic patterns arising in jointly produced sequences reflects turn-taking structure.
678 Specifically, autocorrelations were directly compared between studies at lags 1
679 (corresponding to the turn-taking structure in Study 1), 2 (corresponding to the turn-
680 taking interval in Study 2), and 4 (corresponding to the interval at which full turn cycles
681 repeated in Study 2, i.e. A-A-B-B). Jointly produced sequences in Study 1 displayed greater
682 rhythmicity at lag1 (more negative lag1 autocorrelations) than Study 2, with no between-
683 study difference at lag1 for individually produced sequences. In contrast, jointly produced
684 sequences in Study 2 showed more pronounced rhythmicity at lag4 (more positive lag4

685 autocorrelations) than in Study 1, with no between-study difference in lag4
686 autocorrelations for individually produced sequences. Together, both studies revealed
687 specifically enhanced rhythmicity in jointly produced sequences at the interval of a full
688 turn-cycle (A-B for Study 1, A-A-B-B for Study 2).

689 Interestingly, lag2 autocorrelations (corresponding to the inter-turn interval for Study 2)
690 did not statistically differ between studies in Joint or Individual tasks, suggesting that turn-
691 taking specific temporal patterns arise at the level of turn cycles rather than turn intervals.
692 It should be noted that two extreme lag2 autocorrelation values in the Joint task for Study 2
693 may have reduced the possibility to detect study-specific rhythms at this lag; however,
694 these data points were not removed, as they fell within the overall confidence intervals
695 computed across lags.

696 In sum, turn-taking with a partner gives rise to rhythmic patterns that span across turn-
697 taking cycles, i.e. the interval over which both partners complete one full turn. These
698 temporal patterns are suggestive of motor grouping at the level of turn cycles. Motor
699 grouping has been shown to facilitate acquisition of complex motor sequences.³⁰ Therefore,
700 partners may have attempted to optimize performance in the Joint task by superimposing
701 grouping patterns at the level of turn cycles, either intentionally or unintentionally. It
702 should be noted that turn-taking specific rhythmicities showed difference signs between
703 studies: Lag1 autocorrelations were negative in Study 1, whereas lag4 autocorrelations
704 were positive in Study 2. These differences in sign may be related to the influence of local
705 error correction mechanisms on lag1 autocorrelations but not lag4 autocorrelations.

706 It should also be noted that autocorrelations did not change systematically across blocks in
707 a way that indicated learning (i.e. reduced rhythmicity over time), so it is unclear whether
708 these grouping patterns might become fully attenuated with sufficient training, as partners
709 become more proficient at co-producing temporal intervals. Future work should aim to
710 increase trial length and overall number of trials to assess whether the observed
711 rhythmicities arising from turn-taking structure attenuate with time, as partners become
712 more proficient at coordination. Moreover, future work should assess whether enhanced
713 rhythmicity at early stages of joint action learning predicts more proficient coordination at
714 later stages of joint learning, as would be predicted from studies of motor learning within
715 individuals.

716 **Predictability of sensory outcomes does not facilitate temporal learning**

717 Finally, the sensory outcomes of individuals' actions did not appear to influence learning in
718 either Individual or Joint tasks, as evidenced by Study 1. Specifically, participants showed
719 the same levels of performance and similar patterns of rhythmicity for both Individual and
720 Joint tasks, regardless of whether finger taps produced the same pitch sequence on each
721 trial or different pitch sequences on each trial. This finding is counter to the hypothesis that
722 predictable feedback associated with one's actions should facilitate coordination. This
723 initial hypothesis was based on prior work indicating that sensory feedback about a
724 partner's actions facilitates prediction,¹⁴ and that novices are better at learning how to
725 coordinate the timing of actions when their actions produce highly predictable sensory
726 feedback.¹⁹

727 The observed pattern of results may be explained by recent work suggesting that learning
728 is unaffected by sensory feedback so long as it does not violate spatial contingencies
729 between sound and movement (e.g. ascending motion with descending pitch)¹⁹. In the
730 current task, there was no spatial contingency between sound and action (participants
731 tapped a single key), and therefore the mere presence of sensory feedback may have
732 served as a cue to a partner's timing that facilitate joint action. This interpretation would
733 also be consistent with prior work showing that unstructured feedback associated with
734 joint actions such as single tones¹¹ or haptic feedback¹⁴ are sufficient to facilitate learning
735 to coordinate the timing of actions with a partner. Future work should aim to test this
736 hypothesis by removing auditory feedback associated with joint actions in the present
737 paradigm. If auditory feedback presence was essential for learning to coordinate actions,
738 then coordination should break down in the absence of feedback, suggesting that. feedback
739 presence but not content is critical for joint action learning.

740 It is also possible that the use of pentatonic pitch sequences - which do not give rise to
741 strong harmonic expectancies due to the presence of purely consonant intervals - in the
742 present studies may have prevented participants from developing strong pitch
743 expectancies for Predictable melodies. Had Predictable melodies been composed using
744 scales that generated stronger expectancies, then these expectancies may have given rise to
745 stronger temporal predictions about upcoming sequence events in Predictable relative to
746 Random sequences. Future work should aim to determine whether Predictable melodies
747 that generate stronger pitch expectancies facilitate learning to predict a turn-taking
748 partner's actions relative to Random pitch sequences. Perhaps the influence of pitch
749 expectancies on learning would be greatest in individuals with high scores on musicality
750 indices, who may be more sensitive to pitch expectancy than individuals with lower
751 musicality; future work should also aim to investigate how pitch sensitivity might
752 moderate the influence of pitch predictability on learning to coordinate auditory-motor
753 sequences with a partner.

754 **Conclusions**

755 Taken together, the current work provides one of the first investigations into how partners
756 learn to co-produce temporal sequences in turn-taking, utilizing a novel paradigm that
757 allows for direct comparison between individual and joint sequence learning. Findings
758 from both studies revealed that partners display classic signatures of individual sequence
759 learning when learning to co-produce temporal intervals: increased temporal precision and
760 accuracy with training. Partners did not, however, perform "as one": they did not achieve
761 individual levels of performance with regards to precision, accuracy, or serial dependence
762 between successive intervals. Strikingly, partners superimposed unique rhythms onto joint
763 sequences that were not present during individual learning, and which were related to the
764 turn-taking structure.

765 Rhythmicity is a hallmark of novice motor behaviour, and is often interpreted as a
766 signature of poorly calibrated error correction within-individuals.⁹ The current studies are
767 the first to demonstrate that rhythmicity also characterizes *jointly*-produced temporal
768 sequences. Whether these rhythmicities are driven by an emergent joint timekeeping
769 system between partners - and how this timekeeping system might be influenced by

770 individual timekeeping processes - is an important question for future models of joint
771 action coordination, and an obvious next step.

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Author contributions statement

A.Z., S.D., & N.S. designed the experiments, A.Z. conducted the experiments, A.Z. analysed the results, and all authors wrote and reviewed the manuscript.

Competing interests statement

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data availability

The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study will be made publicly available upon publication.

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